

LPJ-GMINT Protocol

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1 Model history

The LPJ-GUESS-MIGRATION-INTERACTION model (LPJ-GMINT 1.0) couples a module for biotic interactions (INT) to the vegetation dynamic model simulating plant migration, LPJ-GM 3.0. Thus, LPJ-GMINT 1.0 includes spatially-explicit interactions between plants and interacting species.

1.1 LPJ-GUESS

The model LPJ-GM 3.0 (short for LPJ-GUESS-MIGRATION) implements a plant migration module into the dynamic global vegetation model (DGVM) LPJ-GUESS 4.1 (`daily_grass` branch; checked out revision 12699). LPJ-GUESS simulates the physiological processes of plants (e.g. carbon allocation, photosynthesis) along with biogeophysical processes (e.g. soil hydrology) and water/nutrient exchanges in response to input forcing climate (e.g. temperature, precipitation, radiation) [16]

1.2 Plant Functional Type (PFT) concept

In the model, plants are simulated as Plant Functional Types (PFTs), which represent groups of species sharing relatively similar characteristics, such as growth form, life-history strategy, phenology, physiology and bioclimatic limits. PFTs may correspond to individual plant species (e.g. *Picea abies*) or to broader taxonomic groups (e.g. needle-leaved summergreen). The characteristics of PFTs are defined as numerical values (input PFT-specific parameters) in the instruction file (see also Section 7.3.2). These PFT-specific characteristics then determines the local plant dynamics (establishment, growth and mortality) in response to the climate (e.g. minimum temperature for survival and establishment) and competition for space and resources (e.g. light through tree height and water availability through root fraction and depth). See also <https://web.nateko.lu.se/lpj-guess/education/docs/pft.html>.

1.3 LPJ-GUESS `daily_grass` version

In the default model LPJ-GUESS, growth (turnover and carbon allocation) and vegetation dynamics (establishment and mortality) are performed at the end of each year. We employed the `daily_grass` version of LPJ-GUESS where grass tissue turnover and allocation of carbon to reproduction and new biomass are simulated at the end of each day. The simulation of daily growth of grass PFTs allowed us to implement vegetation feedbacks (e.g. grass consumption by interacting species) at the daily level. The formulation of daily grass growth follows the model [3].

1.4 Migration module (LPJ-GM, LPJ-GUESS-MIGRATION)

In the model LPJ-GUESS, seeds are assumed to be always available across the whole simulation domain, thus allowing PFTs to establish as long as environmental conditions are suitable (see [10, 18]).

The migration module of LPJ-GM 3.0 include two options (SEEDISP and FIXSPEED) to simulate plant migration at the start of each year by constraining the seed availability, thus making PFT establishment dependent on migration processes. In the case of the SEEDISP option, migration processes include: (1) seed production depending on leaf area index; (2) seed dispersal via a dispersal kernel; (3) seed bank dynamics including germination and soil longevity; and (4) sapling establishment based on the number of viable seeds in the soil bank.

Differently from the expensive algorithm of SEEDISP with explicit seed dynamics, the FIXSPEED option simulates plant migration by calculating the time delay to full establishment based on a (1) PFT-specific maximum migration rate (given as an input parameter derived from pollen records); (2) the number of years for which seeds are able to survive in an environment not suitable for plant establishment or survival (seed bank longevity); and (3) a leaf area index threshold above which individual plants are able to become seed donors.

For technical details on the parallelization of the migration process, see Section 7.1.

2 Model scope

2.1 The importance of biotic interactions

Range-limit theory [15] identifies three main ecological drivers of species distribution: (1) abiotic factors forming the environmental envelop or fundamental niche within which a species can persist given its physiological limits (ABIO); (2) migration processes through dispersal (DISP), i.e. the ability of individuals to move their propagules (seeds for vascular plants) beyond their current position and expand their distribution (range shift); and (3) biotic interactions (BIO). In summary, range shifts via dispersal (DISP) allow species to persist in changing environments (ABIO). Yet, biotic interactions (BIO) may play a more decisive role in range dynamics either by altering the local environment (e.g. nurse plants creating soil or favorable climatic conditions for seedlings) and dispersal patterns (e.g. pollinators or frugivores), or by directly influencing establishment and extinction lags (e.g. an higher proportion of competitive to facilitative species will make the community more resistant to invasion). Additionally, we should consider that the main effect of range shifts is to reshuffle ecological networks and create novel interactions among its members, which will feed back to form new range limits. Biotic interactions are therefore not only a fundamental driver of range dynamics but one of its main outcome and possibly a driver of global change itself [14].

2.2 The limits of DGVMs in implementing biotic interactions

A variety of novel approaches have emerged in recent years to address the challenge of including BIO in modelling frameworks. However, the wide variety of BIO is still poorly represented [5]. Most DGVMs include BIO as plant-plant competition for light, water, nutrients and/or space in their main framework (i.e. vegetation growth and dynamics). However, there are other types of BIO that may affect the vegetation at different trophic levels and not only in a negative (e.g. large-animal browsing and forest pests and pathogens) but in a neutral (e.g. animal/human trampling where animals/humans stay indifferent to the interaction) or positive (e.g. pollination, animal-mediated seed dispersal, and beneficial soil biota such as decomposers and root symbionts) way [11]. Additional BIO-modules tend to focus on particular cases, as either a specific interaction type (especially negative interactions, such as herbivory) or species (see Section 2.3).

2.3 The progress of DGVMs in implementing biotic interactions

A number of LPJ-GUESS-based models have already been implemented to include additional biotic interactions with feedbacks to the vegetation by coupling a BIO module to the main algorithm of plant dynamics. Some examples are: the spruce bark beetle (*Ips typographus*) module to predict pest

outbreaks in Swedish forests [4]; the population dynamic module for large mammalian grazers [12]; and the generic animal dynamic module, Madingley, which is able to represent the population dynamics of herbivores, omnivores, and carnivores of any size class, along with animal-vegetation feedbacks and heterotrophic food webs [9]. We found only one example [17] of a LPJ-GUESS-coupled model that incorporates both biotic interactions (ungulates, with the same approach as [12]) and migration. With LPJ-GMINT, we aimed to implement a biotic interaction module that is sufficiently generic to include different types of biotic interactions but still account for the diversity of interacting species.

3 Interacting Functional Type (IFT) concept and definition

Following PFTs, we formulated the concept of Interacting Functional Types (IFTs) as groups of species interacting with the vegetation and sharing similar characteristics (as IFT-specific parameters listed in Table 1 and Table 2), including:

- the thermoregulation mode (endotherm or ectotherm), defining the developmental mode;
- the trophic level (carnivore, omnivore, herbivore), defining the feeding order (top-down resource consumption), the compartment to interact with (resource) and its corresponding feedback;
- the bioclimatic limits, defining the thermal tolerances for survival and establishment;
- the life-history traits, defining the ages for gestation, reproduction and longevity (endotherms) or the thermal-dependence for the stage development (ectotherms);
- the foraging type and strategy defining how to access and remove the available resources;
- the dispersal habits; and other attributes.

Parameter	Description	Units
trophic_level	Trophic level (carnivore, herbivore, omnivore)	-
thermoregulation_mode	Thermoregulation mode (endotherm or ectotherm)	-
$M_k^{Juvenile}$	Average body biomass at birth	Grams
M_k^{Adult}	Average body biomass at maturity	Grams
Survival and Activity		
$ifT_k^{Daily,Surv}$	Whether thermal limits are applied at the daily mean temperature (1) or monthly mean temperature (0)	0/1
$T_k^{Surv,Min}$	Minimum temperature for survival	°C
$T_k^{Surv,max}$	Maximum temperature for survival	°C
thr_k^{Active}	Threshold (above) below which the species is (active) inactive	0 – 1
Developmental stage		
$Stages_k$	Life history stages, e.g. [JUV0, JUV1, ADU]	-
$Age_k^{Gestation}$	Length of the gestation time before birth (endotherms)	Days
$Age_k^{Maturity}$	Age at which maturity is reached (endotherms)	Days
Age_k^{Max}	Maximum age of survival, i.e. longevity	Days
$f_{(k,s)}^{devRate}$	Function to calculate the developmental rate for each life history stage (ectotherms)	-
$a^{devRate}, b^{devRate}$	Coefficients of the developmental rate function (ectotherms)	-
$T_U^{devRate}, T_L^{devRate}$	Upper and lower mean temperature boundaries defining the developmental rate (ectotherms)	°C

Table 1: INT module parameters with a brief description, parameter notation, and unit.

Parameter	Description	Units
Foraging		
<code>foraging_type</code>	Whether the herbivores share the available resources evenly among all individuals present in the patch (“ <code>equal_share</code> ”) or monopolize the available resources by blocking the access to other feeding individuals (“ <code>random_competition</code> ”) (herbivores)	-
<code>foraging_strategy</code>	Whether the herbivore consumes a fraction of all available resources at the site (“ <code>fractional_feed</code> ”), or exhaust resources from only one individual host plant at a time before reaching the next (“ <code>unit_feed</code> ”) (herbivores)	-
thr_k^{BS}	Body status threshold below which individuals start to eat	0 – 1
R_k^{Herb}	List of preferred host plants for herbivores	-
$R_k^{Herb,Comp}$	List of preferred compartment for each life stage of herbivores	-
R_k^{Pred}	List of preferred prey species for carnivores	-
$PropR_k$	Proportional preference for resource items (herbivores)	0 – 1
$PropR_k^{Ined}$	Proportion of inedible resources (optional, else 0)	0 – 1
ϵ_k^{Herb}	Proportional herbivore assimilation efficiency	0 – 1
ϵ_k^{Pred}	Proportional carnivore assimilation efficiency	0 – 1
ϕ_k	Proportion of resources consumed based on body mass	0 – 1
$NFrac_k^{Urine}$	Fraction of nitrogen excreted by herbivores	0 – 1
$PropR_k^{Landcover}$	Proportion of available resources by land cover type	0 – 1
Reproduction		
<code>ifViviparity</code>	Whether the reproductive mode is viviparity	0/1
$tint_k^{ReproEvent}$	Interval between reproductive events	Days
γ_k^{Breed}	Proportion of breeding individuals	0 – 1
B_k^{Max}	Maximum number of offspring per reproductive event	Nr.
<code>ifT_k^{Fec}</code>	Whether the calculation of fecundity per reproductive event is temperature dependent (ectotherms)	0 – 1
$f_{(k,s)}^{Fec/Repro}$	Function to calculate the fecundity or (/) the reproductive rate	-
$a^{Fec/Repro}$, $b^{Fec/Repro}$	Coefficients of $f_{k,s}^{Fec/Repro}$ (ectotherms)	-
$T_U^{Fec/Repro}$, $T_L^{Fec/Repro}$	Upper and lower mean temperature boundaries defining $f_{k,s}^{Fec/Repro}$ (ectotherms)	°C
Mortality		
<code>ifdens_k^{Ttree}</code>	Whether maximum carrying capacity is defined by tree volume (1) or by grid cell area (0) (herbivores)	0/1
$dens_k^{Max}$	Maximum density of individuals allowed per grid cell area	Nr./km ²
$dens_k^{MaxTree}$	Maximum density of individuals allowed per tree volume	Nr./km ³
thr_k^{Starv}	Body status threshold below which all individuals starve to death	0 – 1
$Mort_k^{Sap}$	Extra-mortality linked to sapwood consumption (herbivores)	> 1
Migration		
Mig_k^{Speed}	Daily migration speed	m/Days
$MigDays_k^{Wait}$	Waiting time to access neighboring cells	Days
$thr_k^{Disp,Env}$	Threshold below which to disperse based on climate	0 – 1
$thr_k^{Disp,Food}$	Threshold below which to disperse based on per capita available resources	0 – 1
<code>ifMig_k^{Stage}</code>	Which life stages are allowed to migrate	0/1

Table 2: INT module parameters with a brief description, parameter notation, and unit (continuation).

Variable	Description	Units
M_i	Body mass of an average individual of cohort i	Grams
N_i	Abundance of individuals in cohort i	Nr.
Age_i	Age of individuals of cohort i since birth (endotherms) or to the next developmental stage (ectotherms)	Days
BS_i	Body status of individuals of cohort i as the ratio between effective resource intake and maximum resource requirement for metabolic activity	0 – 1
Survival and Activity		
IFT_i^{Active}	Daily boolean defining whether the individuals of cohort i are in the active (1) or inactive (0) season	0/1
IFT_i^{Surv}	Daily boolean defining whether the individuals of cohort i can survive in the grid cell climate	0/1
Developmental stage		
$t_{(b,s)}$	The time since establishment of life stage s	Days
$devRate(i, s)$	Temperature-dependent developmental rate defined as the reverse of the time taken to reach the next life stage s (ectotherms)	0 – 1
Foraging		
ΔM_i^{Ass}	Body mass (of average individual of cohort i) assimilated by the consumed resources	Grams
ζ_i	Daily per capita consumption of biomass of cohort i	Grams
R_i	Daily available resources for cohort i	Grams
$\Delta N_{(n,i)}^{Pred}$	The number of individuals of cohort i died of predation from all predators' cohorts n	Nr.
$Growth_m^{Veg}$	Annual growth of each PFT m calculated as the difference between vegetation biomass at the year start (after growth) and at the end of the previous year (before growth)	
$CMass_{(m,avail)}^{Veg}$	Daily available vegetation (carbon) biomass for cohort i	Grams
$CMass_i^{HerbIntake}$	Total intake of carbon biomass consumed by cohort i (feedback only for herbivores)	Grams
Reproduction		
$ifPregnant$	Whether the average individual of the cohort is currently pregnant (for viviparity)	0/1
B_i^{Count}	Days until the juvenile is born (gestation in viviparity)	Days
$reproRate_i$	Cumulative reproductive rate (temperature-dependent) for the next reproductive event (ectotherms)	0 – 1
N_i^{Breed}	Effective number of breeding individuals of cohort i	Nr.
$B_{i,tot}$	Total growth of cohort i per reproductive event as newly-born individuals	Nr.
Mortality		
ΔN_i^{Mort}	The total number of individuals of cohort i died of non-predation (e.g. illness, starvation, age-related mortality)	Nr.
$N_S^{Mort,Dens}$	Individuals in the grid cell S died due to over-crowding	Nr.
$N_i^{Mort,Starv}$	Individuals of cohort i died due to starvation	Nr.
$N_i^{Mort,Age}$	Individuals of cohort i died due to old age	Nr.

Table 3: State variables of the INT module with notation, a brief description, and unit.

Each simulated grid cell S is characterized by a trophic structure of top-down IFT species and vegetation, where the vegetation is defined by the simulated PFTs according to the LPJ-GUESS routine, and IFT species are simulated according to the INT routine. Although we refer to IFT k as species, taxonomic identity can be up-scaled based on the available data.

Each IFT species k is modelled at the grid cell level as cohorts i . A cohort represents a group of IFT individuals occurring within the same grid cell and sharing the same age. Additionally, we used the concept of stage-based models to classify IFT cohorts in three possible life-history stages based on their reproductive capacity (only adult ADU can reproduce), and whether they eat (only ADU and non-reproductive juveniles JUV1) or are in a non-eating inactive phase (inactive juveniles JUV0).

Each cohort is characterized by four main state variables: (1) body biomass M_i (in grams), (2) abundance of individuals N_i , (3) age in days Age_i since birth for endotherms, or days to the next developmental stage for ectotherms, and (4) the body status, which reflects the resource intake against metabolic requirement as maximum intake, and affects reproduction, mortality and dispersal pressure. Additional state variables are listed in Table 3.

4 Model overview

Figure 1 provides a synthetic scheme of the LPJ-GMINT model.

As initial step, the model reads-in the climate input data and creates the spatial structure to allow the PFT/IFT migration via MPI communication (Section 7.1): definition of the domain size and resolution, assignment of MPI leaders and neighbors for yearly plant migration, and indexing of each cell's neighborhood for daily IFT migration based on the daily migration speed (Section 6.1).

At the start of the simulation, we impose a period (default 500 years) of spin-up time where the vegetation and soil pools reach a dynamic equilibrium. During the spin-up phase PFTs are allowed to establish freely (with no migration restriction) but no IFT establishment/migration is allowed. After the spin-up phase, IFT cohorts are initialized according to the grid cell-specific establishment year with an abundance (Section 5.1) defined by the read-in grid list (Section 7.3.1).

After initial establishment, all IFT ecological processes are executed each day after the completion of the vegetation daily processes (canopy exchanges, soil water accounting, daily carbon allocation, soil organic matter, litter, and methane dynamics).

The processes of IFT population dynamics include:

- bioclimatic survival (IFT-specific thermal tolerance) and activity (dormant or not) depending on the input climatic conditions and the ecology of the species (Section 5.2);
- developmental stage based on age (endotherms) or thermal conditions (ectotherms) (Section 5.3);
- resource consumption based on body mass, where IFT predators feed upon IFT individuals, and IFT herbivores feed upon the LPJ-GUESS vegetation (Section 5.4);
- calculation of body condition as the ratio between the effective resource intake and the maximum resource intake (required for metabolic maintenance and activity) (Section 5.5);
- feedback on the consumed resources (Section 5.6);
- reproduction based on body condition (and thermal conditions for ectotherms) (Section 5.7);
- mortality based on environmental conditions (thermal tolerance), population density (overcrowding), body status (starvation), and age (longevity) (Section 5.8).

After the completion of population dynamics, IFT migration is executed at the end of each day by allowing each cohort to search for a more suitable neighboring cell (according to climate and/or food resources) where to immigrate to, or else to remain in the occupied cell if the climate is suitable and/or

there are sufficient per capita resources (or no better neighboring cell is found) (Section 6.2). Finally, the model output is generated at the end of each year, including (1) the grid cell and life stage specific average of IFT annual body mass, (2) total annual IFT births, (3) total annual IFT deaths, and (4) total amount of resource consumed (specific to the preferred resource items).

Figure 1: Schematic of the model LPJ-GMINT 1.0. LPJ-GMINT 1.0 couples a module for biotic interactions (INT module) to the vegetation dynamic model (LPJ-GUESS algorithm), while allowing both plants (PFTs) and interacting species (IFTs) to migrate (migration module). As illustrated in the upper-left corner, the simulated IFT species at a grid cell are organized in different trophic levels (predators and herbivores), where each IFT species is represented by multiple cohorts (blue circles), and each cohort is represented by age (and related life stages), abundance of individuals (dot number) and average body mass (dot size).

The INT module (upper-left panel) simulates the dynamics of IFT cohorts at the grid cell level through fundamental ecological processes (grey boxes): climate-dependent survival and activity (Section 5.2); development (Section 5.3); resource consumption (Section 5.4) and feedback on consumed resources (Section 5.6); calculation of body status based on metabolic requirement (Section 5.5); reproduction (Section 5.7); and mortality (Section 5.8). The LPJ-GUESS algorithm (upper-right panel) simulates vegetation dynamics each year and allocates plant properties (e.g. leaf carbon mass) at a daily level, which interact with herbivore IFT species.

The migration module (lower-right panel) simulates plant (PFT) migration at the start of each year with two possible modes (SEEDISP and FIXSPEED; see Section 1.4). On the other hand, IFTs can disperse each day depending on the climatic and resource conditions of the focal cell compared to the neighboring cells (IFTMIG; see Section 6).

Relevant processes for the vegetation and interacting species are shown in grey boxes. Variables connecting different processes are shown in yellow boxes, with dashed arrows showing the influence of variables on processes. Solid arrows connect the IFT processes in order.

The following sections (5-6) provide more details on each IFT ecological process with the main mathematical equations.

5 IFT population dynamics

We model the state variables for (1) body biomass M_i of a representative individual of cohort i and (2) abundance of individuals N_i by simplifying the approach by [2]:

$$M_i(t) = M_i(t-1) + \Delta M_i^{Ass}(t) \quad (1)$$

$$N_i(t) = N_i(t-1) - \Delta N_i^{Mort}(t) - \sum_n \Delta N_{n,i}^{Pred}(t) \quad (2)$$

where t is the daily time-step, ΔM_i^{Ass} is the mass assimilated by the consumed resources (Section 5.4.3), ΔN_i^{Mort} is the number of individuals that died of non-predation (e.g. illness, starvation, age-related mortality; Section 5.8), and $\Delta N_{n,i}^{Pred}$ is the number of individuals died of predation from all predators' cohorts n (Section 5.6.2). The feeding order of IFT species is established based on the trophic level, where predators feed first on herbivores, and herbivores feed later on the vegetation. For each IFT species, the order of cohort action depends on the feeding strategy, where cohorts can either have an equal share of the available resources or compete with a random access to the available resources (Section 5.4.3).

5.1 Initialization

After the phase of nitrogen and carbon soil build-up in LPJ-GUESS and the spin-up phase, we establish the initial number of IFT individuals (abundance $N_i(t_0) = N^{Init}$) as a single cohort at a specific simulation year and coordinates. The initial establishment is defined by the grid list (Section 7.3.1) and according to IFT-specific bioclimatic limits for survival (Section 5.2). The established individuals at a site are all adults (stage = ADU) with fixed and species-specific body mass ($M_i(t_0) = M_k^{Adult}$) and ready to reproduce, i.e. for endotherms, the age corresponds to the ‘‘age of maturity’’ ($Age_i(t_0) = Age_k^{Maturity}$), whereas the reverse of the developmental rate (days to the maximum longevity) is calculated based on the grid-specific temperature for ectotherms ($Age_i(t_0) = \frac{1}{devRate_i(t_0)}$; see Eqs. 12-15). Note that in the case of IFT species with an inactive phase (e.g. hibernation), all newly-established cohorts are forced into the active state for the first month to allow the proper calculation of the environmental-related survival (see Section 5.2).

The model implementation of IFT initialization corresponds to the function `modules/ift_dynamics.cpp` \rightarrow `ift_establish_init()`.

5.2 Survival and activity

At the start of each simulation year, we verify whether the IFT species k is able to survive based on bioclimatic conditions:

$$IFT_i^{Surv}(t) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } T_k^{Surv,Min} > T(t) > T_k^{Surv,Max} \\ 1, & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $T(t)$ is the mean temperature (calculated either on a daily or monthly base according to the IFT-specific parameter $ifT_k^{Daily,Surv}$), and $T_k^{Surv,Min}$ and $T_k^{Surv,Max}$ are the species-specific minimum and maximum thresholds for survival, respectively.

If the IFT species k responds to unsuitable climatic conditions by entering an inactive phase (based on thr_k^{Active}), we check each day t whether the IFT species is in its (in)active state. The species enters the inactive state when environmental conditions approach its thermal limits as follows:

$$IFT_i^{Active}(t) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } \mu_S^{Env}(t) < thr_k^{Active} \\ 1, & \text{if } \mu_S^{Env}(t) \geq thr_k^{Active} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where $\mu_S^{Env}(t)$ is the normalized survival probability based on thermal conditions (environmental suitability; 0-1), and thr_k^{Active} is the threshold (above) below which the species is (active) inactive (default = 0.25). The environmental suitability is calculated according to the normal distribution:

$$\mu_S^{Env}(t) = \frac{\exp(-z(t)^2/2)}{\sqrt{2PI}} \quad (5)$$

$$z(t) = \frac{T(t) - T_k^{Surv,Mean}}{T_k^{Surv,sd}} \quad (6)$$

where $T(t)$ is the daily ($ifT_k^{Daily,Surv} = 1$) or monthly ($ifT_k^{Daily,Surv} = 0$) mean temperature, $T_k^{Surv,Mean}$ is the mean between the minimum and maximum temperature for survival ($T_k^{Surv,Mean} = \frac{T_k^{Surv,Min} + T_k^{Surv,Max}}{2}$), and $T_k^{Surv,sd}$ is the standard deviation of the normal distribution as $T_k^{Surv,sd} = T_k^{Surv,Max} - T_k^{Surv,Mean}$. It is then normalized as follows:

$$\mu_S^{Env}(t) = \frac{\mu_S^{Env}(t) - z_{min}(t)}{z_{max}(t) - z_{min}(t)} \quad (7)$$

$$z_{min}(t) = \frac{\exp(-1^2/2)}{\sqrt{2PI}} \quad (8)$$

$$z_{max}(t) = \frac{\exp(-0^2/2)}{\sqrt{2PI}} \quad (9)$$

Note that bioclimatic limits for survival are applied only if the IFT species k is in its active state. The model implementation corresponds to the function `modules/iftdynamics.cpp` → `ift_survive()`.

Figure 2: Example of survival probability based on thermal limits for three IFT species (blue, yellow and red lines) and mean monthly temperature (grey line). Thermal limits for each species are indicated in the legend in parenthesis. Threshold for species activity is indicated by the dashed horizontal line (default = 0.25). Species 3 (red line) enters the inactive state in November and exits it in March.

5.3 Developmental stage

Each cohort of IFT species is defined by its life history stage as JUV0 (inactive juvenile, e.g. fetus or egg, with no food consumption), JUV1 (active non-reproductive juvenile), and ADU (reproductive

adult). All stages s are read-in as a species-specific parameter vector, e.g. [JUV0; JUV1; ADU] meaning [fetus; non-reproductive juvenile; reproductive adult].

The calculation of the change event for the developmental stage differs between endotherms and ectotherms, where endotherms are born (JUV0 \rightarrow JUV1) after a species-specific gestation time ($Age_k^{Gestation}$)

$$stage_{JUV0 \rightarrow JUV1}(t) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } B_i^{Count}(t) < Age_k^{Gestation} \\ 1, & \text{if } B_i^{Count}(t) = Age_k^{Gestation} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

and reach mature adulthood (JUV1 \rightarrow ADU) based on a species-specific age to maturity ($Age_k^{Maturity}$):

$$stage_{JUV1 \rightarrow ADU}(t) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } t_{padu}(t) < Age_k^{Maturity} \\ 1, & \text{if } t_{padu}(t) = Age_k^{Maturity} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where the time (in days) since establishment of life stage JUV0 (conception) and JUV1 (birth) is B_i^{Count} , and the time (in days) from birth to the reproductive adult phase is t_{padu} .

On the other hand, ectotherms change life stage based on a temperature-dependent developmental rate ($devRate_s$). The cumulative developmental rate is defined as the reverse of the time taken to reach the next life stage (in days; e.g. $devRate_{i,s} = 0.1 \rightarrow 10$ days to the next stage $s+1$) and is accumulated daily starting from the first day of each life stage:

$$stage_{s \rightarrow s+1}(t) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } \sum devRate_s(t) < 1 \\ 1, & \text{if } \sum devRate_s(t) \geq 1 \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Figure 3: Example of (a) cumulative and (b) daily developmental rate for the Asian long-horned beetle (*Anoplophora glabripennis*; Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) across a year with monthly mean temperatures: 6, 8, 10, 13, 17, 20, 20, 20, 15, 13, 8, 6 °C. Developmental rates are calculated according to the stage-specific functions of Figure 4.

Default functions for $f_{k,s}^{devRate}$ include a linear relationship, a reverse exponential function, and bounded functions:

$$f_{k,s}^{devRate}(t) = a^{devRate} + b^{devRate} \times T(t) \quad (13)$$

$$f_{k,s}^{devRate}(t) = \frac{1}{a^{devRate} T(t) b^{devRate}} \quad (14)$$

$$f_{k,s}^{devRate}(t) = a^{devRate} \times (T(t) - T_L^{devRate}) \times (T_U^{devRate} - T(t))^{b^{devRate}} \quad (15)$$

where $a^{devRate}$ and $b^{devRate}$ are empirical constants, $T(t)$ is the daily mean temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), and $T_U^{devRate}$ and $T_L^{devRate}$ are the upper and lower IFT-specific temperature thresholds ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) for the developmental stage, respectively.

Figure 4: Example of developmental rate functions for different life stages of the Asian long-horned beetle. The transition egg \rightarrow larva defines the egg hatch into a larval stage as derived by [7] (developmental rate is the hatch rate, 1/day). The developmental rates for larvae (larva \rightarrow pupa) and adult emersion from pupae (pupa \rightarrow juvenile) were defined according to [6] by averaging the parameters across all instars. The transition from an immature to a mature adult (juvenile \rightarrow adult), which indicates the time to the first oviposition, was defined according to [7]. Finally, adult longevity is defined based on daily temperature (adult \rightarrow death) according to [7]. Updated values can be found in [8].

Further developmental models and parameters can be searched in the literature as empirical fit to the focus species (or a closely related species, or genus) by using the R package ‘devRate’ [13].

On the day of the transition to adulthood JUV1 \rightarrow ADU (t^*), we calculate (1) the time (in days) taken to reach maturity (t_{padu}), and (2) start to count the time since maturity ($t_{badu}(t^*) = 0$). These variables are employed in the equations of mortality (Section 5.8).

The model implementation of the developmental stage corresponds to the function `ift_dynamics.cpp` \rightarrow `ift_development()`.

5.4 Foraging

The gathering of resources in the grid cell (calculation of available resources) is determined by the trophic level (where herbivores and carnivores can access only either the vegetation, i.e. herbivory, or animal preys, i.e. predation, respectively, and omnivores can access both) and the foraging preference of each feeding IFT species (Section 5.4.3). The consumption of resources for each cohort (foraging performance) is given by the maximum capacity for resource intake and the amount of individuals competing for the same resources, and thus by the foraging type (sharing of or competition for the resources) and foraging strategy (whether IFT individuals feed upon a fraction of all resources or on a single resource at a time) (Section 5.4.3).

Furthermore, each cohort of IFT species is allowed to consume resources only when its weekly average of body status, which indicates the ratio between the effective and the maximum resource intake (see Section 5.5), falls below a threshold value thr_k^{BS} (default = 1). This approach allows to define

the frequency with which certain species search for food, with individuals of IFT cohorts constantly foraging when $thr_k^{BS} = 1$.

5.4.1 Resource gathering

The type and total amount of resources consumed at a time t , $R_i(t)$, is defined by the foraging preference of feeding IFT individuals for certain PFTs and compartments, i.e. leaf, sapwood, root (herbivory), or IFT (predation) resources:

$$R_k^{Herb} = [PFT_1, \dots, PFT_m] \quad (16)$$

$$R_k^{Herb,Comp} = [\text{leaf}|\text{sapwood}|\text{root}, \dots] \quad (17)$$

$$R_k^{Pred} = [IFT_1, \dots, IFT_j] \quad (18)$$

where the preferred plant compartments $R_k^{Herb,Comp}$ are life stage specific, e.g. sapwood of Norway spruce for *Ips typographus* in its adult stage ADU, and leaf in its larval stage JUV1. The PFT/IFT resources as preferred species m/j are listed in order of preference in $R_k^{Herb/Pred}$. Thus, the foraging preference defines whether a feeding IFT species is a specialist (narrow dietary preference) or a generalist (wider variety of resource items).

Additionally, feeding IFT species can have a proportional preference for resource items:

$$PropR_k = [[0 - 1]_1, \dots, [0 - 1]_{m/j}] \quad (19)$$

where, at equal availability of resources, feeding individuals will forage more upon the resource items with the highest proportional preference (more palatable resources), with $\sum PropR_k = 1$.

The total amount of available resources in the grid cell S for the feeding species k is then calculated for herbivores (predators) across all cohorts o (l) of all preferred PFTs (IFTs) as:

$$R_{S,k}^{Avail,Herb}(t) = \sum_m \sum_o M_{m,o}^{Veg}(t) \quad (20)$$

$$R_{S,k}^{Avail,Pred}(t) = \sum_j \sum_l M_{j,l}^{Prey}(t) \times N_{j,l}^{Prey}(t) \quad (21)$$

where $M_{m,0}^{Veg}$, $M_{j,l}^{Prey}$ and $N_{j,l}^{Prey}$ are the total biomass of the consumed plant PFT m of cohort o , the average biomass of cohort l for prey j , and the abundance of the prey cohort, respectively.

Optionally, we can specify a proportion of “inedible resources”, which corresponds to the amount of resources feeding individuals do not have access to, and/or prevents feeding individuals from entirely removing the vegetation or prey stock. This proportion can be defined as a fixed value given as input for each resource item ($PropR_k^{Ined}$, with $PropR_{m/j,o/l}^{Avail} = 1 - PropR_k^{Ined}$).

Note that in the case of herbivory, the actual biomass available for consumption $M_{m,o}^{Veg}(t)$ needs to be updated at the daily level in the main LPJ-GUESS algorithm as described in Section 5.4.2.

The model implementation of resource gathering corresponds to the function `modules/ift_dynamics.cpp` \rightarrow `ift_resource_gathering()`

5.4.2 Resource daily distribution

In the default LPJ-GUESS model, the cumulative daily Net Primary Productivity (NPP) is allocated to biomass only the last day of the year, when plant growth for the next year (tissue turnover and allocation to reproduction and new biomass) and vegetation dynamics (disturbance, mortality, and establishment) are applied. In the case of the Northern Hemisphere, this means that vegetation biomass increases over winter (31st December), which would be an unrealistic scenario for herbivore consumption. Thus, to better determine the resource availability and feedbacks for herbivores, we

apply a daily simulation of vegetation growth for grass PFTs and shrub/tree PFTs.

To simulate the daily growth of grass and feedbacks from/to the INT module, we use the LPJ-GUESS option `daily_grass`, which allows to calculate the daily turnover of tissue and carbon allocation for grass PFTs (Section 1.3).

For the tree PFT resources, we followed the approach by [17] by calculating the growth of each tree PFT m for one entire year yr as the difference between vegetation biomass at the start of the year (1st January; $CMass_m^{AfterGrowth}$) and at the end of the previous year (31st December; $CMass_m^{BeforeGrowth}$), thus after and before annual growth:

$$Growth_m^{Veg}(yr) = CMass_m^{AfterGrowth}(yr) - CMass_m^{BeforeGrowth}(yr - 1) \quad (22)$$

Similarly to [17], we distribute the annual tree growth across the year based on the weekly rolling average of the variable $phen(t)$ ($phen_7(t)$), which is a proxy of the growth potential of a tree individual as the fraction of potential leaf cover $0 - 1$.

Thus, the actual biomass available for herbivore consumption at day t $M_{m,o}^{Veg}(t)$ depends on the annual growth and leaf cover state. This also accounts for the available nitrogen N according to the C:N ratio $CtoN_i^{bg}$:

$$M_{m,o}^{Veg}(t) = CMass_{m,avail}^{Veg}(t) + \frac{CMass_{m,avail}^{Veg}(t)}{CtoN_i^{bg}(t)} \quad (23)$$

For the daily distribution of resources, we track the available carbon biomass ($CMass_{m,avail}^{Veg}$) of the preferred compartment(s) defined by the life stage-specific preference ($R_k^{Herb,Comp}$).

(a) If the annual growth is positive, we initialize the annual available (carbon) biomass for consumption as the amount of biomass before the annual growth, i.e. as in the end of the previous year.

$$Growth_m^{Veg}(yr) > 0 \rightarrow CMass_{m,avail}^{Veg}(t_0) = CMass_m^{BeforeGrowth}(yr - 1) \quad (24)$$

Then, available daily biomass ($CMass_{m,avail}^{Veg}$) is updated by tracking the biomass already allocated to growth ($Growth_m^{VegAlloc}$).

$$Growth_m^{VegAlloc}(t) = Growth_m^{VegAlloc}(t - 1) + CMass_m^{Veg,Growth}(t) \quad (25)$$

$$CMass_{m,avail}^{Veg}(t) = CMass_{m,avail}^{Veg}(t - 1) + CMass_m^{Veg,Growth}(t) \quad (26)$$

The carbon biomass allocated to growth each day ($CMass_m^{Veg,Growth}$) is calculated according to the change of $phen_7(t)$ as follows:

(a.1) when $phen_7(t)$ decreases from the previous days (which can be a consequence of e.g. drought, and thus no growth), the available biomass corresponds to that of the previous day;

$$CMass_m^{Veg,Growth}(t) = 0 \quad (27)$$

(a.2) when $phen_7(t)$ increases from the previous days (which corresponds to improving bioclimatic conditions, and thus potential growth with $CMass_m^{Veg,Growth}(t) > 0$), the daily available biomass corresponds to that of the previous day plus the daily growth calculated as the “annual growth stock” that has not yet been allocated scaled by $phen_7$;

$$CMass_m^{Veg,Growth}(t) = \max[0; Growth_m^{Veg}(yr) \times phen_7(t) - Growth_m^{VegAlloc}(t)] \quad (28)$$

(a.3) when $phen_7(t) = 1$ all available “annual growth stock” has been allocated (Eq. 28 equals 0), and therefore from this day on the available biomass corresponds to that of the previous day.

(b) If the annual growth is negative (i.e. the biomass of the tree individual is decreasing), we initialize the annual available biomass for consumption on the first day of the year after decrease, and then the available biomass is reduced day after day. In this case, the increase or decrease of $phen_7(t)$ does not matter since we do not need to distribute a potential daily re-growth.

$$Growth_m^{Veg}(yr) \leq 0 \rightarrow CMass_{m,avail}^{Veg}(t_0) = CMass_m^{AfterGrowth}(yr) \quad (29)$$

$$CMass_{m,avail}^{Veg}(t) = CMass_{m,avail}^{Veg}(t-1) \quad (30)$$

The model implementation of the daily carbon allocation for plants corresponds to the function `modules/ift_dynamics.cpp → ift_daily_plant_distribution()`

5.4.3 Resource consumption

The total biomass of resource consumed by each cohort i ΔM_i^{Ass} is modelled as the sum of the total biomass consumed by herbivory ($\Delta M_i^{Ass,Herb}$) and predation ($\Delta M_i^{Ass,Pred}$):

$$\Delta M_i^{Ass}(t) = \Delta M_i^{Ass,Herb}(t) + \Delta M_i^{Ass,Pred}(t) \quad (31)$$

where $\Delta M_i^{Ass,Herb}$ and $\Delta M_i^{Ass,Pred}$ are calculate based on the IFT-specific trophic level as follows:

$$\Delta M_i^{Ass,Herb}(t) = \epsilon_k^{Herb} \zeta_i^{Herb}(t) \quad (32)$$

$$\Delta M_i^{Ass,Pred}(t) = \epsilon_k^{Pred} \zeta_i^{Pred}(t) \quad (33)$$

where ϵ_k^{Herb} is the assimilation efficiency for herbivory (0.5 for herbivores; 0.4 for omnivores; 0 for carnivores), and ϵ_k^{Pred} is the assimilation efficiency for predation (0 for herbivores; 0.64 for omnivores; 0.8 for carnivores). ζ_i is the per capita consumption of biomass defined as the minimum between the maximum resource intake and the per capita available resource R/N :

$$\zeta_i^{Herb}(t) = \min[\zeta_i^{Max}(t); \frac{R_i^{Herb}(t)}{N(t)}] \quad (34)$$

$$\zeta_i^{Pred}(t) = \min[\zeta_i^{Max}(t); \frac{R_i^{Pred}(t)}{N(t)}] \quad (35)$$

where the per capita maximum consumption ζ_i^{Max} includes the cost of body maintenance and activity [1] and is assumed to be proportional to the body mass of the feeding individual by a species-specific constant ϕ_k :

$$\zeta_i^{Max}(t) = \phi_k \times M_i(t) \quad (36)$$

In the case of ectotherms, we may calculate ζ_i^{Max} as the temperature-dependent metabolic cost, including the active and inactive metabolism as field metabolic rate (FMR) and basal metabolic rate (BMR), respectively. This metabolic cost is calculated following [2] as a power-law and exponential function with individual body mass $M_i(t)$ and temperature:

$$\zeta_i^{Max}(t) = E_S \times EFMR + EBMR \quad (37)$$

$$EFMR = I_{0,f}^{FMR} \times \exp\left(-\frac{E_A}{k_B \times T_k^{Body}}\right) \times M_i(t)^{b^{metab,FMR}} \quad (38)$$

$$EBMR = I_0^{BMR} \times \exp\left(-\frac{E_A}{k_B \times T_k^{Body}}\right) \times M_i(t)^{b^{metab,BMR}} \quad (39)$$

where $E_S = 3.7 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ g kJ}^{-1}$ is a scalar to convert energy (kJ) to biomass (g); $I_{0,f}^{FMR} = 1.49 \cdot 10^{11} \text{ eV g}^{-\text{metab,FMR}}$ and $I_0^{BMR} = 4.19 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ eV g}^{-\text{metab,BMR}}$ are FMR and BMR constants independent from mass and temperature; k_B is the Boltzmann constant ($= 5.67 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-4}$); $E_A = 0.69 \text{ eV}$ is an aggregate activation energy of metabolic reactions; T_k^{Body} is the body temperature of an individual in Kelvin, which is assumed to be equal to ambient temperature for ectotherms ($T_k^{Body} = T(t)$); and $b^{\text{metab,FMR}} = 0.88$ and $b^{\text{metab,BMR}} = 0.69$ are body mass exponents for FMR and BMR, respectively. The available resources R_i for each cohort i of each feeding IFT species k is calculated by partitioning the total amount of resources in the grid cell R_S^{Avail} (Eqs. 20-21) according to the amount of competing individuals, the foraging type and strategy, and the relative abundance of available resource items. First, we check whether there are any common resource items ($R_S^{Avail,Com}$) among the IFT species present in the grid cell. If this is the case, each common resource item is split among the IFT species in proportion to the feeding requirement (or foraging pressure), which approximately corresponds to the total biomass of individuals in the grid cell:

$$R_S^{Avail,Com}(t) = R_S^{Avail,Com}(t) \times \frac{M_{S,k}(t) \times N_{S,k}(t)}{\sum M_{S,k}(t) \times N_{S,k}(t)} \quad (40)$$

Next, we calculate the eaten fraction of each resource item m (j) for the herbivore (predator) by multiplying the foraging preference with the relative availability of each resource item:

$$FracR_{m/j}^{Eat} = PropR_k[m/j] \times \frac{R_{S,m/j}^{Avail}(t)}{\sum R_{S,m/j}^{Avail}(t)} \quad (41)$$

The available resource of each cohort i , R_i , is then obtained based on the foraging strategy of the feeding IFT species: (1) **unit_feed**, where the species can access only one resource item at a time and consumes the available resource whole, such as a predator killing a certain prey; (2) **fractional_feed**, where the species eats only a fraction of all available resource items without killing the eaten resource, such as a grazer feeding upon bits of different kinds of herbs and shrubs. According to **unit_feed**, the available resources of each cohort R_i corresponds to the remaining (non-eaten) amount of the resource item with the highest $FracR_{m/j}^{Eat}$, or, in the case of equal $FracR_{m/j}^{Eat}$, to the more abundant resource item. On the other hand, cohorts consuming resources according to **fractional_feed** are able to intake only a fraction of all available resource items; thus, we multiply the maximum possible intake by $FracR_{m/j}^{Eat}$ before calculating the per capita consumption of each resource item:

$$\zeta_i^{Max}(t) = \zeta_i^{Max}(t) \times FracR_{m/j}^{Eat} \quad (42)$$

This approach is based on the concept of frequency-dependent foraging, when an individual feeds upon a certain resource item based on its relative abundance.

The order with which the available resource $R_{S,k}^{Avail}$ is consumed depends on the trophic level of the feeding IFT species, where carnivores eats first, followed by omnivores and herbivores. Next, the order with which the feeding cohorts of each IFT species remove available resources depends on their foraging type. If the feeding IFT species share the available resources evenly among all individuals present in the grid cell (foraging type = **equal_share**), we calculate the per capita consumption of each cohort ζ_i by dividing the total available resources by the total grid cell abundance (per capita available resource is $\frac{R_i}{N_{S,k}(t)}$). This type of strategy is adopted when the acquisition of resources is helped by the presence of other individuals (e.g. group hunting) or when the abundance of resources allows for evenly spaced consumption (e.g. grazing on a savannah). Alternatively, feeding IFT cohorts can monopolize the available resources by blocking the access to other feeding individuals (foraging type = **random_competition**). In this case, we loop through all cohorts of the grid cell in a random order (randomized each foraging event) and progressively remove the per capita consumed resources (per capita available resource is $\frac{R_i}{N_i(t)}$) from the total available amount until exhaustion.

Figure 5: Example of resource consumption (kg biomass) for two resource items with different palatability (0.80 vs. 0.20) based on foraging strategy (*fractional_feed* or *unit_feed*) and type (*equal_share* or *random_competition*). The amount of consumed resource is averaged among three cohorts with (body mass, abundance): (4, 10), (5, 15), (6, 12).

Finally, we calculate the total amount (grid cell S) of consumed resources of each item m (j) for the herbivore (predator) by multiplying the per capita consumption with the cohort abundance and summing up over all cohorts (and over all IFT species in the case of common resource items):

$$R_{S,m}^{Cons,Herb}(t) = \sum \zeta_i^{Herb}(t) \times N_i(t) \quad (43)$$

$$R_{S,j}^{Cons,Pred}(t) = \sum \zeta_i^{Pred}(t) \times N_i(t) \quad (44)$$

The model implementation of resource consumption corresponds to the function `modules/ift_dynamics.cpp` \rightarrow `ift_resource_consumption()`.

5.5 Body status

We calculate the body status of each individual $BS_i(t)$ (with values 0–1) as the ratio between potential resource intake and metabolic cost given by the maximum resource intake, following the concept of the body condition based on fat deposit from [12]:

$$BS_i(t) = \min\left[\frac{\zeta_i(t)}{\zeta_i^{Max}(t)}; 1.0\right] \quad (45)$$

5.6 Feedback

The total amount of consumed resources for each grid cell is removed by herbivory (Section 5.6.1) and/or predation (Section 5.6.2). Thus, we apply a feedback from the feeding IFTs to each resource item as defined by the IFT-specific preference and consumed resources (Section 5.4.3).

5.6.1 Herbivory feedback

Feedback on the vegetation involves removal of consumed biomass and (potentially) re-growth of the eaten plant.

Adjust plants based on eaten biomass

To remove the consumed biomass from each eaten PFT cohort i , we partition the total biomass intake of herbivores $R_S^{Cons,Herb}$ to carbon and nitrogen biomass by using the original carbon to nitrogen ratio (C:N ratio):

$$FracC_i(t) = \frac{CMass_i(t)}{CMass_i(t) + NMass_i(t)} \quad (46)$$

$$CMass_i(t) = CMass_i(t-1) - CMass_i^{Eaten}(t) \quad (47)$$

$$NMass_i(t) = NMass_i(t-1) - NMass_i^{Eaten}(t) \quad (48)$$

When consumed resources are removed by unit (foraging type = `unit_feed`), the total amount of consumed biomass is eaten progressively looping through all cohorts and starting from the cohort with the most abundant resources:

$$CMass_i^{Eaten}(t) = (CMass_i(t) + NMass_i(t)) \times PropR_{m,o}^{Avail}(t) \times FracC_i(t) \quad (49)$$

$$NMass_i^{Eaten}(t) = (CMass_i(t) + NMass_i(t)) \times PropR_{m,o}^{Avail}(t) \times (1 - FracC_i(t)) \quad (50)$$

$$R_S^{Cons,Herb}(t) = R_S^{Cons,Herb}(t-1) - CMass_i^{Eaten}(t) - NMass_i^{Eaten}(t) \quad (51)$$

where $1 - PropR_{m,o}^{Avail}(t)$ is the proportion of inedible resources (Section 5.4.1).

When consumed resources are removed fractionally (foraging type = `fractional_feed`), we distribute the total eaten biomass proportionally to the biomass available at each cohort i :

$$R_i^{Eaten}(t) = R_S^{Cons,Herb}(t) \times \frac{CMass_i(t) + NMass_i(t)}{\sum (CMass_i(t) + NMass_i(t))} \quad (52)$$

$$CMass_i^{Eaten}(t) = R_i^{Eaten}(t) \times FracC_i(t) \quad (53)$$

$$NMass_i^{Eaten}(t) = R_i^{Eaten}(t) \times (1 - FracC_i(t)) \quad (54)$$

Next, we need to move the consumed carbon of leaves and roots to the corresponding litter compartments (note that the PFT compartment corresponding to the eaten C and N biomass depends on the IFT-specific preference $R_k^{Herb,Comp}$):

$$CLitter_i^{Leaf}(t) = CLitter_i^{Leaf}(t-1) + CMass_i^{Eaten,Leaf}(t) \quad (55)$$

$$CLitter_i^{Root}(t) = CLitter_i^{Root}(t-1) + CMass_i^{Eaten,Root}(t) \quad (56)$$

Instead, all the carbon of the killed sapwood needs to be converted to heartwood:

$$CMass_i^{Heart}(t) = CMass_i^{Heart}(t-1) + CMass_i^{Eaten,Sap}(t) \quad (57)$$

In the case of sapwood as resource, the consumed N will go to the heartwood:

$$NMass_i^{Heart}(t) = NMass_i^{Heart}(t-1) + NMass_i^{Eaten,Sap}(t) \quad (58)$$

On the other hand, the nitrogen of the eaten leaves and/or roots will be moved to the soil as N available for plants by a IFT-specific fraction $NFrac_k^{Excr}$. This represents the N excreted by herbivores as urine or feces, which we assume to be directly taken up by plants (whereas N in the litter compartments has a slower cycling of nutrients):

$$NMass_{Soil}^{Avail}(t) = NMass_{Soil}^{Avail}(t-1) + \Delta NMass_{i,m}(t) \times NFrac_k^{Excr} \quad (59)$$

$$NLitter_{i,m}(t) = NLitter_{i,m}(t-1) + \Delta NMass_{i,m}(t) \times (1 - NFrac_k^{Excr}) \quad (60)$$

Note that in the case N cycling is not active, all N should go to the litter (Eq. 60).

Finally, we update some of the PFT properties that will affect the daily canopy fluxes – leaf area index (LAI_i) and foliar projective cover (FPC_i) – based on the changes of the biomass compartments:

$$LAI_i(t) = CMass_i^{Leaf}(t) \times SLA_k \quad (61)$$

$$FPC_i(t) = 1 - \exp^{-0.5 \times LAI_i(t)} \quad (62)$$

where SLA_k is the PFT-specific parameter specific leaf area.

As a last step in the herbivory feedback, we kill PFT individuals and transfer their biomass to the litter based on (1) their updated allometry and biomass compartments, i.e. if one compartment falls below a certain threshold (minimum carbon mass allowed kgC/m^2 , $MINCMASS = 1.0 \cdot 10^{-8}$); (2) and sapwood removal. In the case of (2), an extra-mortality is added to the consumption of sapwood since bark removal can be devastating depending on the feeding species. This sapwood mortality is calculated proportionally to the eaten sapwood and to an IFT-specific extra-mortality for sapwood removal ($Mort_k^{Sap}$):

$$\mu_i^{Sap}(t) = \frac{\Delta CMass_i^{Sap}(t) \times Mort_k^{Sap}}{CMass_i^{Sap}(t-1)} \quad (63)$$

Thus, tree individuals are killed when their probability of sapwood mortality exceed 1.

Figure 6: Example of tree mortality linked to sapwood consumption by herbivores (sapwood eaten as a proportion of total available biomass) and an herbivore-specific parameter for the proportional increase of tree mortality ($Mort_k^{Sap}$; different colors). $Mort_k^{Sap} = 1$ means that tree mortality with and without bark removal by herbivores is the same. Tree individuals are killed when sapwood mortality exceeds 1.

The whole PFT population is removed if all of its individuals are killed (i.e. the density of individuals is negligible).

The model implementation of the feedback for herbivory corresponds to the function `ift_dynamics.cpp` \rightarrow `ift_feedback_herbivory()`.

Adjust plants based on daily re-growth.

In the case of re-growth given by daily allocation ($CMass_i^{Veg,Growth} > 0$ for trees, case **a.2** in Section 5.4.2), we distribute the biomass increment ($CMass_i^{Veg,Growth}$) among the tissue compartments ($\Delta CMass_i$):

$$CMass_i^{Veg,Growth}(t) = \Delta CMass_i^{Leaf}(t) + \Delta CMass_i^{Root}(t) + \Delta CMass_i^{Sap}(t) \quad (64)$$

while satisfying the (tree) allometric relationships (`growth.cpp` \rightarrow `allocation()` in LPJ-GUESS) for the (tree) properties of height ($height_i$), stem diameter ($diam_i$), stem volume (vol_i), and crown area ($crown_i$):

$$height_i(t) = \frac{CMass_i^{Sap}(t) \times k_k^{latosa}}{woodens_k \times CMass_i^{Leaf}(t) \times SLA_k} \quad (65)$$

$$diam_i(t) = \frac{height_i(t)^{1/k_k^{allom3}}}{k_k^{allom2}} \quad (66)$$

$$vol_i(t) = height_i(t) \times PI \times diam_i(t)^2 \times 0.25 \quad (67)$$

$$crown_i(t) = \min[k_k^{allom1} \times diam_i(t)^{k_{rp}k}; crown_k^{Max}] \quad (68)$$

where PI is the mathematical constant ~ 3.14159 , and the PFT-specific parameters k_k^{allom1} , k_k^{allom2} and k_k^{allom3} correspond to constants in the allometric equations, and $crown_k^{Max}$ to the maximum tree crown area.

The leaf to sapwood area ratio is defined by a PFT-specific parameter k_k^{latosa} . On the other hand, the balance between roots and leaves is defined by the variable $ltor_i$:

$$CMass_i^{Sap}(t) = CMass_i^{Leaf}(t) \times woodens_k \times height_i(t) \times SLA_k \times k_k^{latosa} \quad (69)$$

$$CMass_i^{Root}(t) = \frac{CMass_i^{Leaf}(t)}{ltor_i(t)} \quad (70)$$

The leaf to root ratio ($ltor_i$) is based on the water limitation ($wscal_i^{Mean}$) and current leaf to root status ($ltor_i^{Status}$) (Eq. 71), and additionally on nitrogen N limitation ($nscal_i^{Mean}(t)$) (Eq. 72) when active (as done in the `daily_grass` approach):

$$ltor_i(t) = wscal_i^{Mean}(t) \times ltor_k^{Max} \times ltor_i^{Status}(t) \quad (71)$$

$$ltor_i(t) = \min[wscal_i^{Mean}(t); nscal_i^{Mean}(t)] \times ltor_k^{Max} \times ltor_i^{Status}(t) \quad (72)$$

$$ltor_i^{Status}(t) = \frac{ltor_k^{Max}}{CMass_i^{Leaf}(t)/CMass_i^{Root}(t)} \quad (73)$$

where $ltor_k^{Max}$ is the PFT-specific parameter defining the leaf to root mass ratio under non-water-stressed conditions.

Thus, we derive a function for the increment of leaf carbon to solve with numerical methods (`growth.cpp` \rightarrow `allocation()` in LPJ-GUESS):

$$\Delta CMass_i^{Leaf}(t) = k1 \times k0a - k0b \quad (74)$$

$$k0a = b - \Delta CMass_i^{Leaf}(t) - \frac{\Delta CMass_i^{Leaf}(t)}{ltor_i(t)} + CMass_i^{Heart}(t) \quad (75)$$

$$k0b = \frac{(b - \Delta CMass_i^{Leaf}(t) - (\Delta CMass_i^{Leaf}(t)/(ltor_i(t))))^2}{(CMass_i^{Leaf}(t) + \Delta CMass_i^{Leaf}(t)) \times k3} \quad (76)$$

with:

$$k1 = k_k^{allom2} \frac{2}{k_k^{allom3}} \times \frac{4}{PI/wooddens} \quad (77)$$

$$k2 = 1 + \frac{2}{k_k^{allom3}} \quad (78)$$

$$k3 = \frac{k_k^{latosa}}{woodens_k/SLA_k} \quad (79)$$

$$b = CMass_i^{Sap}(t) + CMass_i^{Veg,Growth}(t) - \frac{CMass_i^{Leaf}(t)}{ltor_i(t)} + CMass_i^{Root}(t) \quad (80)$$

Next, we calculate the increments in the other tissue compartments:

$$\Delta CMass_i^{Root}(t) = \frac{\Delta CMass_i^{Leaf}(t) + CMass_i^{Leaf}(t)}{ltor_i(t)} - CMass_i^{Root}(t) \quad (81)$$

$$\Delta CMass_i^{Sap}(t) = CMass_i^{Veg,Growth}(t) - \Delta CMass_i^{Leaf}(t) - \Delta CMass_i^{Root}(t) \quad (82)$$

Finally, we update the carbon and nitrogen pools for each tissue compartment (leaves, roots, sapwood and heartwood), where the corresponding change in N for each compartment is based on the C:N ratio before growth ($CtoN_i^{bg}$):

$$CMass_i(t) = CMass_i(t-1) + \Delta CMass_i(t) \quad (83)$$

$$\Delta NMass_i(t) = \frac{\Delta CMass_i(t)}{CtoN_i^{bg}(t-1)} \quad (84)$$

$$NMass_i(t) = NMass_i(t-1) + \Delta NMass_i(t) \quad (85)$$

The model implementation of the daily vegetation re-growth corresponds to the function `iftdynamics.cpp` \rightarrow `daily_plant_regrowth()`.

5.6.2 Predation feedback

In the case of IFT individuals of cohort i being preys, we remove the number of preys $\Delta N_{n,i}^{Pred}$ killed by all predator individuals (N_n) of cohorts n corresponding to the total predated (consumed) biomass $R_{S,j}^{Cons,Pred}$ (Eq. 44). The total predated biomass for each cohort is proportionally removed based on the total biomass of the prey cohorts:

$$R_{i,j}^{Cons,Pred}(t) = R_{S,j}^{Cons,Pred}(t) \times \frac{M_i(t) \times N_i(t)}{\sum M_i(t) \times N_i(t)} \quad (86)$$

We then calculate the corresponding abundance of killed preys by dividing the total predated biomass with the average biomass of the cohort and taking the ceiling (as a proportion of eaten prey most likely corresponds to the death of the whole prey):

$$\Delta N_{n,i}^{Pred}(t) = \text{ceil} \left| \frac{R_{i,j}^{Cons,Pred}(t)}{M_i(t)} \right| \quad (87)$$

The model implementation of the feedback for predation corresponds to the function `iftdynamics.cpp` \rightarrow `ift_feedback_predation()`.

5.7 Reproduction

In the case of endotherms, a reproductive event can happen after an interval of days given by the IFT-specific parameter $tint_k^{ReproEvent}$. In the case of ectotherms, a reproductive event can happen when the cumulative reproductive rate (as the sum of daily reproductive rates) exceeds the unit ($reproRate_i > 1$), i.e. the reverse of the cumulative reproductive rate indicates the number of days until the next reproductive event. The daily reproductive rate depends on daily mean temperature according to an IFT-specific function ($f_{k,s}^{Repro}$, possible options at Eqs. 13-15). Thus, the reproductive rate can be interpreted as the developmental rate between the adult (ADU) and newly-born stage (JUV0) (see Section 5.3).

If the reproductive event is possible, we calculate the per capita fecundity $B_i(t)$, which is defined by body condition and an IFT-specific maximum fecundity B_k^{Max} :

$$B_i(t) = BS_i(t) \times B_k^{Max} \quad (88)$$

Optionally for ectotherms ($ifT_k^{Fec} = 1$), B_k^{Max} can be calculated based on ambient temperature, $B_k^{Max} = f_{k,ADU}^{Fec}(T(t))$, by applying one of the temperature-dependent functions used to calculate the developmental rate (Eqs. 13-15) and the IFT-specific parameters a^{Fec} , b^{Fec} , T_U^{Fec} , T_L^{Fec} .

We assume that only a fraction of the adult cohort can reproduce, with $N_i^{Breed}(t)$ being the effective number of breeding individuals, and λ_k^{Breed} being the proportion of breeding individuals in the population of species k (e.g. females, by default $\lambda_k^{Breed} = 0.5$):

$$N_i^{Breed}(t) = \lambda_k^{Breed} \times N_i(t) \quad (89)$$

So that the total growth of the cohort per reproductive event is:

$$B_{i,tot}(t) = N_i^{Breed}(t) \times B_i(t) \quad (90)$$

We assume no energy cost for gestation or lactation.

Additionally, the IFT-specific parameter $ifViviparity$ defines whether the reproductive mode of the IFT species is viviparity ($ifViviparity = 1$), i.e. the embryo grows within the mother body as a fetus (JUV0) before being born as partially developed juvenile (JUV1). After a period of gestation ($B_i^{Count} = Age_k^{Gestation}$; Eq. 10) of the “pregnant mother cohort” ($ifPregnant = 1$), a cohort of active juveniles of abundance $B_{i,tot}$ is established with the average body mass of a juvenile ($M_k^{Juvenile}$) and the body status of the mother cohort. In the reverse case ($ifViviparity = 0$), we establish new individuals of abundance $B_{i,tot}$ with null body mass and in the inactive juvenile stage (JUV0 as eggs) and the body status of the mother cohort. Upon hatching (JUV0 \rightarrow JUV1 defined by the developmental stage; see Section 5.3), the cohort will be assign the average body mass of a juvenile ($M_k^{Juvenile}$). The model implementation of IFT reproduction corresponds to the function `modules/ift_dynamics.cpp \rightarrow ift_reproduction()`. The model implementation of newly-born cohorts corresponds to the function `modules/ift_dynamics.cpp \rightarrow ift_establish_birth()`.

5.8 Mortality

Mortality due to environmental conditions exceeding the thermal limits of the IFT species is implemented according to Eq. 3 (Section 5.2). In the case thermal limits are exceeded, all cohorts of the grid cell are removed.

If the cohorts manage to survive the environmental conditions of the grid cell, mortality is modelled in three additional ways: (1) stochastic daily density-dependent mortality; (2) deterministic daily starvation mortality, which is related to body conditions; (3) stochastic daily age-dependent mortality, which is related to maximum longevity and is applied only to adult cohorts. The total number of individuals that die of non-predation is modelled as:

$$\Delta N_i^{Mort}(t) = N_S^{Mort,Dens}(t) + N_i^{Mort,Starv}(t) + N_i^{Mort,Age}(t) \quad (91)$$

The probability of IFT individuals dying due to over-crowding (e.g. by easier spread of diseases) across all cohorts S is modelled by a logistic function:

$$\mu_S^{Dens}(t) = \frac{dens_k^{Max}}{1 + \exp(-k^{Dens} \times (dens_S(t) - dens_k^{Mid}))} \quad (92)$$

where IFT-specific parameter $dens_k^{Max}$ is the maximum density (nr. of individuals per km²) that a grid cell can sustain, k^{Dens} is the increasing rate ($\frac{10}{dens_k^{Max}}$), $dens_S$ is the total density in the grid cell (i.e. across all cohorts), and $dens_k^{Mid}$ is the mid-point of maximum carrying capacity (default $dens_k^{Mid} = \frac{dens_k^{Max}}{1.5}$). The total density in the grid cell is calculated by dividing the total grid cell abundance (N_S , nr. of IFT individuals) by the area of the grid cell ($cellArea$ in km²), where the area is calculated as a segment of a hemisphere of radius R (6371.2213 km) from the equator to a parallel (circular) plane h vertical units towards the pole:

$$dens_S = \frac{N_S}{cellArea} \quad (93)$$

$$cellArea = s \times \frac{\Delta x}{360} \quad (94)$$

$$s = 2PI \times R \times (h1 - h2) \quad (95)$$

$$h1 = R \times \sin(y^{Top} \times \frac{PI}{180}) \quad (96)$$

$$h2 = R \times \sin(y^{Bot} \times \frac{PI}{180}) \quad (97)$$

$$y^{Top} = y + 0.5\Delta y \quad (98)$$

$$y^{Bot} = y^{Top} - \Delta y \quad (99)$$

where y , y^{Top} , and y^{Bot} are the coordinates of the latitude for the center, top and bottom of the grid cell.

In case of $ifdens_k^{Tree} = 1$, the probability of density-dependent mortality is based on the amount of individuals allowed on a tree, which conceptually reflects the ecology of IFT species performing their population dynamics on single trees (e.g. tree pests) contrary to free-ranging species. First, we calculate the total tree volume ($\sum_m vol_m(t)$ in m³) of all host plants m in the grid cell according to Eq. 67.

Next, we calculate the total density of individuals per tree volume m³ in the grid cell by dividing the total abundance of IFT individuals in the grid cell by the total tree volume in the cell:

$$dens_{S,tree}(t) = \frac{N_S(t)}{\sum_m vol_m(t)} \quad (100)$$

The probability of IFT individuals dying due to over-crowding on a tree in the grid cell is modelled by the logistic function of Eq. 92, where $dens_k^{Max}$ is maximum density (nr. of individuals per tree volume m³) that host trees can sustain ($dens_k^{MaxTree}$) and $dens_S(t)$ is $dens_{S,tree}(t)$.

The total number of individuals of cohort i killed due to over-crowding is then calculated by scaling the abundance of the cohort with the mortality if the density-related mortality is higher than a randomly drawn number between 0 and 1:

$$N_i^{Mort,Dens}(t) = \begin{cases} N_i(t) \times \mu_i^{Dens}, & \text{if } rand(0, 1) \leq \mu_i^{Dens} \\ 0, & \text{if } rand(0, 1) > \mu_i^{Dens} \end{cases} \quad (101)$$

The starvation-dependent mortality is cohort-specific, where individuals of cohort i are killed proportionally to the weekly rolling average the body status, $RA(BS_i(t); 7d)$, if the weekly average of the

body status of the cohort falls below a threshold (default $thr_k^{Starv} = 0.1$):

$$N_i^{Mort,Starv}(t) = \begin{cases} N_i(t) \times RA(BS_i(t); 7d), & \text{if } BS_i(t) \leq thr_k^{Starv} \\ 0, & \text{if } BS_i(t) > thr_k^{Starv} \end{cases} \quad (102)$$

Age-dependent mortality is calculated at the cohort-level following [2]:

$$\mu_i^{Age}(t) = \lambda_i^{Age} \times \exp \frac{t_{padu}}{t_{badu}} \quad (103)$$

where λ_i^{Age} is the instantaneous rate of age-dependent mortality at the point of maturity, t_{badu} is the time as days before reaching maturity, and t_{padu} is the number of days since the point of maturity. λ_i^{Age} can be derived from Eq. 103, if assuming that $\mu_i^{Age}(t) = 1$ when the age of maximum longevity (Age_k^{Max}) is reached, i.e. $t_{padu} = Age_k^{Max} - t_{badu}$:

$$\lambda_i^{Age} = \frac{1}{\exp \frac{Age_k^{Max} - t_{badu}}{t_{badu}}} \quad (104)$$

A fraction of the cohort is killed proportionally to the age-dependent mortality if this is higher than a randomly drawn number between 0 and 1:

$$N_i^{Mort,Age}(t) = \begin{cases} N_i(t) \times \mu_i^{Age}, & \text{if } rand(0, 1) \leq \mu_i^{Age} \\ 0, & \text{if } rand(0, 1) > \mu_i^{Age} \end{cases} \quad (105)$$

The model implementation of IFT mortality corresponds to the function `modules/iftdynamics.cpp` \rightarrow `ift_mortality()`.

6 IFT migration (IFTMIG)

The migration of IFT species (IFTMIG) is implemented as daily movement among neighboring cells (Section 6.1) prompted by a probability of movement (or dispersal pressure) (Section 6.2).

6.1 Set-up neighboring cells for migration

At the beginning of the simulation, we identify the neighboring cells of each grid cell (as indexed position within the spatial domain) and IFT species (IFT-Gridcell object) based on a search radius given by the daily migration speed of the moving species (Mig_k^{Speed} in meters per day).

$$Radius_k^{Disp} = Mig_k^{Speed} \quad (106)$$

We then calculate the haversine distance (in meters) between the center of the focal cell f and all other cells s in the simulation domain:

$$Dist_{n,i}^{xy}(t) = R \times 1000 \times c \quad (107)$$

$$c = 2 \times 2(\sqrt{a}, \sqrt{1-a}) \quad (108)$$

$$a = \sin^2(\Delta\phi/2) + \cos\phi_f \times \cos\phi_s + \sin^2(\Delta\lambda/2) \quad (109)$$

$$\Delta\phi = y_s - y_f \quad (110)$$

$$\Delta\lambda = x_s - x_f \quad (111)$$

$$\phi_f = y_f \times rad_{eq} \quad (112)$$

$$\phi_s = y_s \times rad_{eq} \quad (113)$$

where R is the earth's radius (6,371 km), rad_{eq} is the radians equivalents to coordinate degrees (0.017453292519943295), x and y are longitude and latitude (in degrees), respectively.

Indexed positions of accessible neighboring cells are then stored in the IFT-Gridcell object (vector of integer indexes) when their distance to the focal cell is lower than the IFT-specific search radius.

Note that the resolution of the simulation grid should be considered in relation to the migration speed of the simulated IFT species. For example, with a spatial resolution (e.g. 0.5 degrees; see Figure 7) much coarser than the daily search radius (e.g. 0.5 km per day) no neighboring cells will be stored in the index vector. In this case, we implement a waiting time $Days^{Wait}$ to access neighboring cells n up to 1 month (30 days) by multiplying the search radius by the number of waiting days until we manage to find a set of accessible neighboring cells.

$$x_n, y_n \rightarrow (Radius_k^{Disp} \times Days^{Wait}) \geq Dist_{n,i}^{xy}(t) \quad (114)$$

In the reverse case, a spatial resolution (e.g. 0.01 degrees; see Figure 8) much higher than the daily search radius (e.g. 5 km per day) would result in a high number of stored neighboring cells across which we would need to loop daily, with a subsequent high computation load.

Figure 7: Example of neighboring grid cells given different IFT-specific search radius and focal cell positions. The focal cell is in grey, with the corresponding neighboring cells in highlighted cells. The numbers within each cell indicate the distance in km from the center of the focal cell. The number of waiting days before moving to neighboring cells is reported in each matrix title. This example presents a grid with 0.5 degrees of spatial resolution.

As a general rule, the daily search radius of simulated IFT species should not exceed the spatial resolution of the simulation domain in order to avoid high computational loads. In the case of multiple species with different magnitudes of migration speed, it is thus suggested to adopt the coarser

resolution and impose a waiting time to access neighboring cells on the slower moving species. Neighboring cells are set up in the function `framework/framework.cpp` \rightarrow `findneighbours_on_leader()`.

Figure 8: Visualization of a grid with 0.01 degrees of spatial resolution and distances from the focal cell (grey) in meters. See legend of Figure 7 for more details.

6.2 Dispersal pressure

IFT cohorts can move proportionally to (1) the available per capita resources and (2) the environmental conditions at each neighboring cell compared to the focal cell. Individuals do not necessarily disperse every day but are prompted by dispersal cues: (1) when the body status of a cohort and (2) the environmental suitability fall below certain thresholds, $thr_k^{Disp, Fodd}$ (note that $thr_k^{Disp, Fodd}$ should be higher than the starvation threshold thr_k^{Starv} ; see Eq. 102):

$$if_{Disp_i, k}^{Food}(t) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } BS_i(t) < thr_k^{Disp, Fodd} \\ 0, & \text{if } BS_i(t) \geq thr_k^{Disp, Fodd} \end{cases} \quad (115)$$

and $thr_k^{Disp, Env}$:

$$if_{Disp_s, k}^{Env}(t) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \mu_s^{Env}(t) < thr_k^{Disp, Env} \\ 0, & \text{if } \mu_s^{Env}(t) \geq thr_k^{Disp, Env} \end{cases} \quad (116)$$

Note that the necessary condition for a cohort to migrate is that its current life stage is allowed to move according to the ecology of the species (this is defined by $if Mig_k^{Stage}$), e.g. a pupa (JUV0) cannot migrate.

The assessment of migration cues for all cohorts is performed by the function `framework/framework.cpp`
 \rightarrow `ift_migration_prepare()`.

Figure 9: Example of dispersal, where the dispersal pressure (colors and numbers in each cell) changes with each day-step. At each step, the focal cell (grey) “moves” to the neighboring cell (highlighted) with the highest dispersal value. This example presents a grid with 0.01 degrees of spatial resolution and a search radius of 15 meters per day.

In case the dispersal cue for food is realized ($if_{Disp_i,k}^{Food} = 1$), a proportion of individuals $N_{i,mig}(t)$ from the cohort i migrates. This proportion is calculated based on the maximum number of individuals allowed in the cohort before reaching starvation $N_{i,max}(t)$:

$$N_{i,mig}(t) = \max[0; N_i(t) - N_{i,max}(t)] \quad (117)$$

$$N_{i,max}(t) = \text{floor} \left\lfloor \frac{R_f^{Avail}(t)}{thr_k^{Starv} \times \zeta_i^{Max}(t)} \right\rfloor \quad (118)$$

where $N_{i,max}$ is calculated by assuming a body status corresponding to the starvation threshold and a per capita resource intake as the per capita available resources in the grid cell (cf. with Eq. 45):

$$thr_k^{Starv} = \frac{R_f^{Avail}(t)}{N_{i,max}(t)/\zeta_i^{Max}(t)} \quad (119)$$

To select the neighboring cell for immigration, we calculate the dispersal pressure for food by comparing the per capita available resources at the focal cell f ($\frac{R_f^{Avail}(t)}{N_f(t)}$) and at each n -th neighboring

cell ($\frac{R_n^{Avail}(t)}{N_n(t)}$), thus accounting for food palatability and the competition of other individuals at the potential incoming cell:

$$Disp_n^{Food}(t) = \frac{R_n^{Avail}(t)/N_n(t)}{R_f^{Avail}(t)/N_f(t)} \quad (120)$$

where the incoming cell has the highest $Disp_n^{Food}$, if greater than 0. If no neighboring cells are found with better food conditions ($Disp_n^{Food} > 1$), individuals of the focal cohorts do not move.

In case the dispersal cue for environmental condition is realized ($if_{Disp_{S,k}}^{Env} = 1$), we move all individuals to a neighboring cell with better environmental conditions ($\max[Disp_n^{Env}] \rightarrow Disp_n^{Env} > 0$) than the focal cell:

$$Disp_n^{Env}(t) = \mu_S^{Env}(t) \quad (121)$$

$$N_{i,mig}(t) = N_i(t) \quad (122)$$

If both conditions are realized, all individuals in the grid cell are moved (Eq. 122) and the dispersal pressure is a weighted sum of food and environmental conditions, with environmental conditions accounting for 90% of the sum:

$$Disp_n^{Press}(t) = 0.1Disp_n^{Env}(t) + 0.9Disp_n^{Food}(t) \quad (123)$$

After finding a suitable neighboring cell for immigration (if it exists), the cohort information is transferred to the neighboring patch with the most abundant resources. Finally, we can sum-up the immigrants to the respective cohorts (of the same age), or create a new cohort in case it does not exist in the incoming grid cell.

The calculation of dispersal pressure and the search for a suitable neighboring cell are performed by the master node (or leader rank 0; see more in Section 7.1) in the function `framework/framework.cpp` \rightarrow `iftmigrate_on_leader()`. The update of re-distributed cohort information is performed by the function `framework/guess.cpp` \rightarrow `get_iftmigration_msg()`.

7 Technical information

LPJ-GMINT is written in ANSI C++ (as the base-code LPJ-GUESS) and uses MPI distributed parallelism to simulate plant and animal migration among grid cells.

7.1 MPI parallelization and computational efficiency

7.1.1 Multiple masters and non-blocking asynchronous communication (SEEDISP)

The spatial domain of LPJ-GMINT is represented by an ensemble of grid cells (with a dispersal path of 1 km²), which are divided among the MPI tasks. In the SEEDISP option, the amount of seeds produced by trees in each grid cell is communicated to a set of master-ranks at the start of each year. Following a dispersal algorithm, these master-ranks redistribute the seeds over the whole spatial domain and communicate the amounts of arriving seeds back to each grid cell (slave-ranks), where the main LPJ-GUESS code simulates local vegetation dynamics [10]. However, the MPI protocol may also have limitations concerning the ratio between the total number of simulated cells (spatial extent) and the number of available nodes (or processes per CPU), which is an inherent characteristic of the HPC cluster available for the simulation. That is, in the case of great spatial extents, it is necessary to use multiple master-ranks to optimize the calculation of seed dispersal (convolution with FFT). According to the default MPI protocol of LPJ-GM 1.0 and 1.1, the slave-ranks have to wait for all master-ranks to finish the calculation (i.e. to receive the seeds from the respective master) before proceeding with the simulation on their rank. However, with a high number of simulated cells, it might happen that a

master-rank would be assigned as a slave to another master-rank (and vice versa). This would result in a deadlock in the simulation (MPI knot). To solve this issue, we added non-blocking asynchronous communication (MPI_Ibse and MPI_Recv), which can also increase the overall performance of the MPI parallelization.

7.1.2 One master and low-cost migration algorithms (FIXSPEED and IFTMIG)

As a further improvement on computational efficiency, the FIXSPEED and IFTMIG options employ less mechanistic and less costly algorithms to simulate plant and animal migration. These low-cost algorithms requires the use of one master-rank only (leader rank 0) where migration-related messages from all slave-cells are gathered and the re-distribution of information (either as potential for establishment or movement of IFT cohort individuals) is realized. Both blocking and non-blocking MPI schedules are possible, although it is suggested to use non-blocking asynchronous communication with a high number of grid cells to decrease the computational time (especially in the FIXSPEED option). Finally, these low-cost algorithms allow the use of coarser spatial (>1 km) and taxonomic (parametrization possible above the species level) resolutions, and thus the simulation of range shift dynamics and biotic interactions at large (or fine) spatial and temporal scales.

7.2 How to build LPJ-GMINT

In order to build the model LPJ-GMINT, the following scientific libraries are required: GCC, OpenMPI, FFTW and NetCDF-HDF5. Multiple CPUs are also required to use the MPI parallelization of all migration routines. The model can be applied in parallel on a number of different Linux cluster systems. Before building the model, please check the CMake configuration file (CMakeLists.txt) in the main folder. To build LPJ-GUESS, the build system cmake needs to be installed. If it's not installed it can be downloaded for free from www.cmake.org.

After entering the main folder of the model, the following line commands need to be executed to build the model:

```
cd LPJ-GMINT #enter main model folder
rm -r build #remove the old build directory
mkdir build #make a new build directory to compile
cd build #move into the new build directory
```

It is possible to build different versions of the model:

1. the default LPJ-GUESS model (without plant migration nor IFT dynamics and migration):
USE_MIGRATION=OFF and USE_INTERACTION=OFF;
2. the LPJ-GM model (with plant migration): USE_MIGRATION=ON;
3. the LPJ-GMINT model (with IFT dynamics and migration): USE_INTERACTION=ON;

These different options can be set through flags after the cmake command as shown below. The plant migration and interaction module can be used at the same time (USE_MIGRATION=ON and USE_INTERACTION=ON), although this is not mandatory. Mind that to use the plant migration (USE_MIGRATION=ON) and the interaction (USE_INTERACTION=ON) modules, the activation of the MPI schedule is required (USE_MPI=ON).

```
cmake -DUSE_MPI=ON -DUSE_INTERACTION=ON -DUSE_MIGRATION=ON ..
# activate all modules but not the compression (.zip) of the output
make
```

When the model is built, a target `guess` file is generated in the build folder.

7.3 How to run LPJ-GMINT

7.3.1 How to generate a grid list

Each line of the grid list should contain the following information (separated by space /tab) in this precise order:

- longitude (decimal degrees);
- latitude (decimal degrees);
- PFT1-name (e.g. BIBS);
- `year_establishment`, the year of PFT1 establishment (in simulation years); `year_migration`, the starting year of PFT1 migration (in simulation years);
- etc... for all simulated PFTs;
- IFT1-name;
- `init_year`, the year of IFT1 establishment (in simulation years);
- `init_abu`, the initial cohort abundance of IFT1 at the coordinate (number of individuals);
- `lc_type`, the land cover type at the coordinate (default is FOREST);
- etc... for all simulated IFTs.

A one-line example (i.e. one forested grid cell) in which all PFTs are allowed to establish from the start but do not migrate, and the IFT is not allowed to establish (thus having zero abundance):

```
8.46    47.65    PFT1    0    60000    PFT2    0    PFT3    0    60000    IFT1
60000    0    FOREST
```

Note that if you do not wish for the PFT to establish at a site (used to match current observations, e.g. removal of trees in cities or fields), the first year of PFT establishment should be set to 60000, that is at a sufficiently high value to never be reached during the simulation time: `year_establishment > years_total`. Otherwise, the first year of establishment should be set to 0, i.e. the PFT establishes as soon as the bioclimatic conditions allow it. Values of IFT establishment (`init_year`) should be set in the same way.

Similarly, if the PFT does not migrate, the starting year of migration is set to 60000, that is at a sufficiently high value to never be reached during the simulation time: `year_migration ≥ years_total`. Otherwise, the first year of migration should be set to a value following the spin-up time but lower than the total simulation time: `nyear_spinup > year_migration < years_total`.

The initial cohort abundance of newly-established IFTs (`init_abu`) should be preferably defined based on ecological information regarding the maximum group size of the species or alternatively the maximum IFT density in the grid cell area (by summing the cohort abundances across all simulated patches).

Land-cover types (`lc_type`) can be derived from contemporary observations (e.g. <https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/corine-land-cover/>). In case of paleo-simulation, all values are set to the default FOREST.

7.3.2 How to generate an instruction file

Default parameters in the instruction file are defined for the global settings of the simulations and PFT-specific settings. The model comes with parametrized instruction files in the folder `data/ins/` (`europe.ins` for European simulations and `global.ins` for global simulations). For more information on the default parameter settings of the instruction file, see the LPJ-GUESS official webpage: <https://web.nateko.lu.se/lpj-guess/education/docs/insfile.html>. Newly-added global simulation settings are reported in Table 4.

Global parameter	Definition
<code>bool ifdailygrass</code>	whether to active the <code>daily_grass</code> routine (see Section 1.3)
<code>xstring state_path_save</code>	path to directory where to save the model states
<code>xstring state_path_restart</code>	path where to find the saved model states to restart from
<code>int state_year_restart</code>	start state file (no setting = after spin-up time)
<code>int state_year_save</code>	first year to start saving state files
<code>int state_year_save_interval</code>	interval in which to save state files
<code>xstring migration_mode</code>	whether to enable migration with seed dynamics (<code>SEEDISP</code>) or with fixed migration speed (<code>FIXSPEED</code> or <code>FIXSPEED_LOOP</code>)
<code>xstring mpisend_mode</code>	whether to send messages via <code>MPI_IbSEND</code> or <code>MPI_send</code> (<code>MPI_IBSEND</code> , better for many leaders and large grid list) or (<code>MPI_SEND</code>)
<code>int years_total</code>	number of years to run the simulation for
<code>int year_start</code>	start year from which to run the simulation
<code>int output_interval</code>	number of years between each output year
<code>bool temporal_averaging</code>	whether the values are averaged over the <code>output_interval</code>
<code>bool output_year_BP</code>	whether the output year is reported as BP (1) or astronomical year (1)
<code>double dispersal_patchsize</code>	patch size for dispersal calculations (km ²)
<code>double FIXSPEED_MAXRADIUS</code>	maximum seed dispersal radius for the fixed migration speed <code>FIXSPEED</code>
<code>int cutfftkernel</code>	number of cells at which to cut the kernel in the fft simulation
<code>vector<double> domain(4)</code>	lon, lat extremes and spatial resolution
<code>vector<double> subdomain(4)</code>	lon, lat size and division in subdomains
<code>int EDGE_CELLS_X</code>	number of cells that the fft simulation is extending over the array, lon direction
<code>int EDGE_CELLS_Y</code>	number of cells that the fft simulation is extending over the array, lat direction

Table 4: New global parameters.

Newly-added IFT-specific parameters are listed in Table 1 and Table 2 and can be gathered as follows:

- the animal trait database “traitdata” (through the R package `traitdata`; see <https://github.com/RS-eco/traitdata>) and the Animal Ageing and Longevity Database (AnAge, <https://genomics.senescence.info/species/index.html>) for life history traits;
- <https://animaldiversity.org/> for dietary preferences, density and dispersal habits.

7.3.3 How to submit a job

The model comes with a shell script (`submit.sh`) to run the model as a parallel application by submitting a job on systems implementing MPI, OpenPBS and SLURM. The `submit.sh` requires the following input values:

- `NPROCESS` = number of processes in parallel job. Should be a multiple of the compute cores per node. For example on the COSMOS HPC, it is a multiple of 48 (<https://www.lunarc.lu.se/systems/cosmos/>). A “strong scaling experiment” can determine the optimal number of nodes based on the HPC system (https://hpc-wiki.info/hpc/Scaling#Strong_Scaling_2).
- `WALLTIME` = maximum wall (real) time for job hh:mm:ss. It can be estimated based on a “weak scaling experiment” (https://hpc-wiki.info/hpc/Scaling#Weak_Scaling_2).
- `INSFILE` = path to ins file from run directory.
- `INPUT_MODULE` = input module to use. LPJ-GMINT allows only two input module: “mpi” and “cf”. See Section 7.3.3 for further details.
- `GRIDLIST` = path to gridlist file from run directory.
- `OUTFILES` = list of LPJ-GUESS output files in single quotes, and separated by spaces (filenames only, including extension, no directory.) Shell wildcards are allowed. Output files are defined in the instruction file. See Section 7.3.2.

Example:

```
NPROCESS=96
WALLTIME=00:10:00
WALLTIME_APPEND=00:05:00 #time required to unite all outputs
# from sub-directories run to one output in the main run directory
INSFILE=guess.inz
INPUT_MODULE=mpi
GRIDLIST=gridlist.txt
OUTFILES='*.out'
```

- `mpi` as defined in the C++ file `/modules/paral_mpi.cpp`. This input module is used to perform paleo-simulation by reading-in the LPJ-GUESS formatted paleo-climate originally generate by Armstrong et al. (2019) (available at <https://doi.org/10.5285/4ca242208e904efe830af45f1697f730>). The LPJ-GUESS formatted paleo-climate is read-in as 2500-years time-slices starting from the oldest time in BP years as indicated by the input parameter `year_start`. The paleo-climate used for the spin-up time stars from `year_start` until `year_start + nyear_spinup`. For example, `year_start=22000`, `nyear_spinup=500` and `years_total=5000` means that the simulation will start at 22,000 years BP (before present) with a spin-up time forced by the climate from 22,000 to 21,501 BP; the vegetation dynamics will start at 21,500 BP until 17,000 BP; or...
- `cf` as defined in the C++ file `/modules/cfinput.cpp`. This input module is used to perform contemporary or future simulations with a properly formatted input climate (see formatted CRU data files). In this case, the spin-up time is forced by the climate cycling over first `NYEAR_SPINUP_DATA` (default 30) years from the start of the simulation. For example, `year_start=2010`, `nyear_spinup=500` and `years_total=511` means that the spin-up time corresponds to the range 2010-2040, and this will keep cycling until 500 years of simulation are reached (if the climate data does not reach 2040, the cycling range will simply be 2010-end year of climate data); the vegetation dynamics will start at 2010 until 2021.

Different version of the `submit.sh` based on different Linux cluster systems can be found in the folder `parallel_version`. Once executed, the `submit.sh` will create NPROCESS sub-directories (`run1`, `run2`, etc), separate the gridlist into the sub-directories, and submit the job; after queuing, the simulation will start running. Please check the comments in the templates for more details on the shell scripts operations. To run a job, run the following command lines:

```
cp parallel_versio/submit.tmpl run_main/submit.sh #copy the correct
# template of the submit script as a shel file in the main run directory
sh submit.sh #execute the submit script
```

When the simulation is completed the terminal will print ‘Finished; in all sub-directories and the full output files will be generated in the main run directory.

8 More information

For all newly-implemented LPJ-GMINT features, please find the code lines within `USE_INTERACTION` declarations.

For more details on the LPJ-GUESS model, please check <https://web.nateko.lu.se/lpj-guess/education/docs/starthere.html>.

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